

Bryophyte diversity in the gypsum outcrops of Sicily (Italy)

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Abstract: A study on the bryophyte diversity of 12 Sicilian gypsum outcrops, falling in 4 Nature Reserves and 5 Special Areas of Conservation (SAC), is presented in order to increase knowledge about this peculiar flora for which conservation efforts need to be addressed. The bryoflora consists of a total of 85 taxa, 8 liverworts and 77 mosses, most of them belonging to the *Pottiaceae* family and characterized by xero-morphological adaptations. The bio-ecological analysis has emphasized the prevalence of xerophytic and basiphytic species with life form turf and life strategy colonist. Regarding the gypsicolous character, only one species, *Tortula revolvens*, behaves as a strict gypsophyte, and a small group of species (*Aloina* spp., *Crossidium* spp.) as wide gypsophytes. The bryofloras of the sites show a quite high diversity level in species composition and include some rare and interesting taxa for Italy, e.g. *Acaulon triquetrum*, *Aloina brevirostris*, *Syntrichia handelii*, *Tortula brevissima*, *Tortula revolvens*, *Tortula solmsii*, *Petalophyllum ralfsii*. This study, which improves the information on the gypsum flora, represents a contribution to the knowledge of a habitat which is today considered a priority for conservation.

Keywords: bryophytes; conservation; gypsum; Sicily

Introduction

Gypsum outcrops are widespread in many regions of the world and host a considerable biological diversity (Escudero et al. 2015). The gypsum habitats constitute refuge stations for plant species, whose presence is to relate with the past climatic phases; they occur as island-like outcrops and support unusual floras very rich in endemic plants, contributing to some of the most remarkable biodiversity hotspots in terrestrial ecosystems (Palacio et al. 2007, Musarella et al. 2018). The species and the plant community growing on gypsum represent a clear example of the strict relationship between soil and vegetation, as many plant species grow exclusively or preferentially on such peculiar substrates (Musarella et al. 2018, Pérez-García et al. 2018). The gypsum outcrops often represent geological islands interrupting the uniformity of other surrounding landscapes; here it is favoured the occurrence of plants with a narrow distribution (Moore et al. 2014) on nutrient-unbalanced, water-limited soils (Merlo et al. 1998, 2001, Musarella et al. 2018).

Gypsum substrates have particularly stressful physical and chemical properties for the life of plants as they involve an intense nutritional impoverishment of the soil (Mota et al. 2011, Palacio et al. 2007), especially in arid or semi-arid environments, as the high evaporation determines a capillary rise of gypsum on the superficial layers of soil which involve the recrystallization of gypsum and the formation of gypsum crusts; in mesic or humid environments, water washout prevents the development of gypsum crust (Escudero et al. 2015).

The formation of a gypsum crust in the ground constitutes a physical obstacle to the germination of the seeds of vascular plants (Romao & Escudero 2005). Furthermore, the low water retention of gypsum soils leads to a high infiltration of rainwater, which increases the water deficit during periods of dryness (Guerrero Campo et al. 1999). The high osmotic pressure of the soil solution, a consequence of the solubility of gypsum, also reduces the ability of plants to extract water from the soil (Herrero & Porta 2000). In addition, gypsum soils have adverse chemical characteristics, nutritional deficiency mainly caused by the exchange of calcium with other ions retained in the soil complex (Meyer et al. 1992), and by the high concentration of sulphate ions which can be toxic to

plants (Ruiz et al. 2003). Leaf chemical composition is a good predictor of the degree of plant specialization to gypsum soils; in particular, the high concentration of sulphates is the element that best discriminates between gypsophytes and not gypsophytes or gypsosvags (Merlo et al. 2019).

Bryophytes, with lichens and cyanobacteria, constitute the gypsum biological soil crusts, one of the most typical component of the gypsum ecosystems, considered important drivers of ecosystem processes such as carbon and nitrogen cycling, water infiltration and soil stability (Escudero et al. 2015). The selectivity of these environments is highlighted by the presence of species with xerophytic adaptations known as xeropottoid and xerothal-loid syndrome respectively in mosses and liverworts (Kürschner 2004).

Despite the peculiarity of its flora and vegetation, the gypsum substrates have been for a long time an underestimated or ignored habitat in Italy, with serious consequences for their conservation. As regards the phanerogamic flora, recently an elaborate checklist of the Italian gypsophilous vascular flora was published in the ambit of the GYPWORLD Project, funded by the European Commission under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme/MSCA-RISE-2017. Concerning the bryophyte flora, a richness of information is known for Spain (i.e., Martínez-Sánchez et al. 1991, Guerra et al. 1992, 1993, 1995, Puche & Gimeno 1995, Salmerón et al. 2011); for Italy, only few contributions regarding some gypsum outcrops of Sicily (Privitera 1989, Marino et al. 2017) and Emilia Romagna (Aleffi et al. 2014), as well as other data taken from more extensive works (Lo Giudice & Cristaudo 2004, Lo Giudice & Bonanno 2010), were published.

Aim of this work is to provide a broad knowledge of the bryophyte flora of the gypsum outcrops of Sicily in order to focus on this peculiar habitat for which conservation efforts need to be addressed.

Material and methods

Study areas

Gypsum outcrops are usually formed in shallow marine basins under arid to semi-arid climatic conditions and with a very low feeding of terrigenous siliciclastic sediments from continental areas (De Waele et al. 2017). In the Mediterranean basin these conditions occurred during the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC), a peculiar climatic/physiographic circumstance that modified the connection between the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea (Hsü et al. 1977, Roveri et al. 2001). In Italy, most gypsum outcrops belong to the Gessoso-Solfifera Formation (GSF) of Messinian age. This formation is typical of almost all the palaeogeographic domains of the whole Apennine chain and Sicily, and is the main geological evidence of the “Messinian salinity crisis”. The most complete succession of GSF crops out in central and south-western Sicily and occupy a large surface when compared with the surface of all gypsum outcrops of the Italian peninsula. Here, we find two evaporitic successions laying upon pelitic facies of the Terravecchia Formation and locally on white diatomitic marls (Tripoli Formation), and covered by fine pelagic sediments (Trubi Formation), (De Waele et al. 2017). The gypsum is poorly permeable substrate, very friable and subject to erosive processes that give a “young” character, preventing the formation of deep and advanced soils. The Sicilian territory is characterized by a Mediterranean climate, diversified on the basis of the altitudes and slopes. The average annual temperature is 17–18 °C in the coastal areas, and 16 °C in the most inland areas. Precipitation is concentrated in autumn and winter with an average of 500-700 mm/year. According to the bioclimatic classification of Rivas-Martínez et al. (2011), the bioclimate of the investigated sites is of the Mediterranean pluviseasonal oceanic, ranging from lower thermomediterranean to lower meso-mediterranean thermotype and from lower dry to upper semiarid ombrotype (Pesaresi et al. 2014).

Sampling methods

The floristic study is based on unpublished and literature data. As regards the unpublished data, the field work was carried out during 2018–2019 years; the season of the collection was spring or late spring. The surveys and samplings were done on the gypsum outcrops in sites referred to the provinces of

Caltanissetta, Palermo, Trapani, Agrigento. The literature data refer to sites of the Enna and Catania provinces and, partially, to Caltanissetta and Agrigento, too (Privitera 1989, Lo Giudice & Cristaudo 2004, Lo Giudice & Bonanno 2010). The list of the sites (Fig. 1) is reported below.

Palermo province:

Site 1: Rocca di Entella – plateau (municipality of Contessa Entellina), 483 m a.s.l., 37°46'24.1" N, 13°06'58.4" E, gypsum crusts, bioclimate upper thermomediterranean up- per dry.

Site 2: Rocca di Entella – Monte Castelluccio (municipality of Contessa Entellina), 477 m a.s.l., 37°46'19.5" N, 13°07'17.2" E, selenite gypsum, bioclimate upper thermome- diterranean upper dry.

Site 3: Serre di Ciminna (municipality of Ciminna), 473 m a.s.l., 37°51'59" N, 13°33'23" E, selenite gypsum, bioclimate lower mesomediterranean upper dry.

Caltanissetta province:

Site 4: Monte Conca (municipality of Campofranco), 385 m a.s.l., 37°29'32" N, 13°42'56" E, selenite gypsum, bioclimate upper thermomediterranean lower dry. Bryophyte diversity in the gypsum outcrops of Sicily (Italy)

Site 5: Passo di Piazza (municipality of Gela), 88 m a.s.l., 37° 2'26.33" N, 14°22'15.31" E, clayey-gypsum, bioclimate lower thermomediterranean upper semiarid.

Site 6: Caltanissetta outskirts (from Lo Giudice & Bonanno 2010), marl-gypsum and gypsum oucrops, bioclimate lower mesomediterranean upper dry.

Trapani province:

Site 7: RNI Grotte di S. Ninfa (municipality of S. Ninfa), 400 m a.s.l., 37°46'48" N, 12°53'51" E, selenite gypsum, bioclimate upper thermomediterranean upper dry.

Agrigento province:

Site 8: Monte Poliscia (municipality of Licata), 59 m a.s.l., 37°06'29" N, 13°52'35" E, clayey-gypsum, bioclimate lower thermomediterranean upper semiarid.

Site 9: SP 23 Casteltermini, 140 m a.s.l., 37°29'37" N, 13°40'40" E, (from Privitera 1989), selenite gypsum, bioclimate upper thermomediterranean lower dry.

Site 10: SP 22 Casteltermini, 164 m a.s.l., 37°30'28" N, 13°41'02" E, (from Privitera 1989), selenite gypsum, bioclimate upper thermomediterranean lower dry.

Enna province:

Site 11: Enna outskirts (from Lo Giudice et al. 1997, Lo Giudice & Cristaudo 2004, Lo Giudice & Bonanno 2010), gypsum outcrops, bioclimate upper mesomediterranean lower subhumid.

Catania province:

Site 12: Raddusa outskirts (from Lo Giudice & Bonanno 2010), gypsum outcrops, biocli- mate lower mesomediterranean lower dry.

The identification of the outcrops was carried out through the preliminary analysis of the geological map of Sicily Lentini & Carbone 2014); moreover, the field delimitation of the gypsum outcrops was

carried out taking into account the vascular gypsophilous vegetation as practical guide for recognition of gypsum soil.

The bryophytes were sampled from: open, dry gypsum soil (a); sheltered gypsum soil (b); more and less humid gypsum soil (c); marl-gypsum soil (d); dry clayey gypsum soil (e); gypsum rocks with accumulated soil (f); gypsum rocks (g); hollows of sheltered rocks (h); at the base of gypsum rocks (i); marl-gypsum rocks (l), (Table 1).

Some of the investigated sites fall within protected areas, such as Integral Nature Reserve “Grotta di Entella” (site 1 and site 2), Oriented Nature Reserve “Serre di Ciminna” (site 3), Integral Nature Reserve “Monte Conca” (site 4), Integral Nature Reserve “Santa Ninfa” (site 7), and/or within the SAC of Natura 2000 network: ITA050006 Monte Conca (site 4), ITA020024 Rocche di Ciminna (site 3), ITA020042 Rocche di Entella (site 1 and site 2), ITA010022 Complesso Monti di Santa Ninfa - Gibellina e Grotta di Santa Ninfa (site 7), ITA050012 Torre Manfreda, Biviere e Piana di Gela (site 5).

Data analyses

For the biological analysis we have considered the life forms reported in Hill et al. (2007) and life strategies in Dierßen (2011), and in Dia & Campisi (2015), Puglisi et al. (e.g., 2014, 2016, 2019a, 2019b). The life forms represent the general appearance of a colony of bryophytes resulting from the growth model, branching and general assembly of individuals. Life strategies, based on the reproduction and dispersal strategies, reflect the ecological site conditions and give knowledge on the mechanisms of habitat maintenance, establishment, re-establishment of species and communities. Life forms and life strategies reflect the correlation of ecological site conditions and prevailing taxa/communities (e.g., Kürschner & Frey 2013, Puglisi et al. 2012, 2013a, 2013b, 2019a, 2019b).

The ecological analysis of the bryoflora was made by utilizing the Ellenberg indicator values of moisture and soil acidity. Using the same scale of Ellenberg for the phanerogams, the ecological indicator values have been assigned to the bryophytes by Düll (1991), and subsequently updated and validated by Hill et al. (2005, 2007) to which we refer in this paper. For moisture (F) the values range from 1 (indicator of extreme dryness) to 12 (normally submerged); for substrate acidity (R), from 1 (indicator of extreme acidity) to 9 (on substrata with free calcium carbonate, mainly chalk and limestone).

In addition, on the basis of the personal knowledge and field experience, as well as of data inferred from literature (Guerra et al. 1992, 1993, 1995, Puche & Gimeno 1995, Aleffi et al. 2014, Marino et al. 2017), the functional groups of gypsophily were attributed to each species, according to those reported by Musarella et al. (2018) for the vascular plants. They are the followings: accidental (species very rare or absent on gypsum); gypsovag (species that may be abundant on gypsum, although they could be even more frequent on other types of substrates); wide gypsophytes (species for which gypsum and other highly related substrates are their preferred habitats); strictly gypsophytes (species that do not live outside gypsum substrates, except accidentally).

Multivariate analysis on floristic data was performed using SYN-TAX 2000 software (Podani 2001). A hierarchical classification method (UPGMA) was performed; dissimilarity was measured using the Jaccard coefficient.

The list of the liverworts and mosses is reported in alphabetical order in Table 1; the nomenclature of the taxa follows Söderström et al. (2016) for liverworts, Ros et al. (2013) for mosses.

Results

On the Sicilian gypsum outcrops a total of 85 bryophyte taxa were identified (Table 1), with a strong prevalence of mosses (77) respect to the liverworts (8); among the mosses, the acrocarpous species (66) are strongly prevalent. The ratio liverworts/mosses (l/m) is 0.10 and ratio pleurocarpous/acrocarpous (p/a) 0.17 (Table 2).

The moss flora is characterized by the dominance of the *Pottiaceae* species (58.4%), followed at a distance by the *Brachytheciaceae* (11.7%), including almost all the pleurocarpous detected in the

investigated areas, *Bryaceae* (9.1%), *Funariaceae* (3.9%), *Dicranaceae* (3.9%). The percentage of the remaining families is negligible. As concerns the liverworts, the *Fossombroniaceae*, with 5 taxa corresponding to 62.5%, is the prevailing family.

Analyzing the biological behaviour of each species, represented by life forms and life strategies, which are closely related to ecological conditions, the biotype turf is strongly dominant (65.5%), due to the high presence of *Pottiaceae* species (Table 3). This biotype is followed by a much lower percentages of mat (14.3%), tuft (8.4%), solitary (4.8%), weft and cushion (3.5% each one). As concerns the life strategy, a strong occurrence of colonist species is observed (65.5%); these species can be regarded as pioneers colonizing hard environments, prevailing in dry and sun-exposed sites or underlying a strong disturbance (Puglisi et al. 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015). This strategy is followed by the per-ennial with 15.5% (typical of undisturbed stable environments), annual shuttle (11.9%), long-lived shuttle (3.5%), and short-lived shuttle (2.4%); the fugitive life strategy is represented only by *Funaria hygrometrica*.

Considering the examined ecological indices, with regard to moisture the xerophytic species prevail with values 1–3 corresponding to 38.1%, and value 4 to 27.4%; in particular, some species spread on the gypsum habitats (*Tortula revolvens*, *Crossidium squamiferum*) can be considered as indicators of extreme dryness (value 1). As the reaction of the substrate, the basiphytic species strongly prevail (values 6–9: 88.1%), with the highest values (8–9) in *Crossidium* spp., *Aloina* spp., *Didymodon* spp., *Gymnostomum* spp., *Cephaloziella baumgartneri*, etc.

As regards the functional groups concerning gypsophily, only *Tortula revolvens* behaves as a strict gypsophyte. The incidence of wide gypsophytes (7.1%) is low, represented by the species of the genera *Aloina* and *Crossidium*. Certainly, the most numerous functional group is represented by the gypsovags (64.7); among this category, the species of the genera *Didymodon*, *Pseudocrossidium*, *Trichostomum*, *Barbula* are the most spread. Finally, the accidental species contribute with 27.1%.

The dissimilarity among the bryofloras of the studied sites is always higher than 50% (Fig. 2). In the constructed dendrogram it is observed 2 main floristic groups, A and B, the last one including only the floras of sites 5 and 8. The group A comprises the clusters A1, A2 and A3; within the cluster A2, a closer relation can be noted among the floras of sites 9 and 10, and sites 11 and 12.

Some species found in the Sicilian gypsum outcrops are rare or very rare in Italy; they are *Acaulon triquetrum*, *Aloina brevirostris*, *Crossidium crassinervium*, *Gyroweisia reflexa*, *Syntrichia handelii*, *Tortula brevissima*, *Tortula revolvens*, *Tortula solmsii* and *Petalophyllum ralfsii*.

In the investigated sites, the species colonize several microhabitat, especially open, dry gypsum soil, gypsum rocks and gypsum rocks with accumulated soil (Table 1).

Discussion and conclusion

The Sicilian gypsum outcrops host a bryophyte flora mostly represented by acrocarpous mosses, a small number of pleurocarpous mosses and liverworts, with a clear xerophytic and basiphytic character in accordance with the climate characteristics and the peculiar typology of the gypsum substrate. This is confirmed also by the low ratio liverworts/mosses and pleurocarpous/acrocarpous, the high incidence of *Pottiaceae* whose high incidence is justified by the presence in this family of species well adapted to dry environments and therefore tolerant of long drought periods. In particular, among the *Pottiaceae*, the occurrence of species with xeropottoid syndrome is to mention. This syndrome is represented by the presence of hyaline hairs in the leaves (*Crossidium*, *Tortula*, *Syntrichia*), revolute leaf margins and/or concavity (*Crossidium*, *Tortula*, *Pseudocrossidium*, *Didymodon*), papillose or mammillose cells (*Syntrichia*, *Tortula*, *Microbryum*, *Trichostomum*), turgid cells (*Syntrichia*, *Tortula*) or enlarged cells (*Aloina*), spirally twisted leaves when dry, leaves with lamellae or filaments (*Crossidium*, *Aloina*), (Frey & Kürschner 1988, Guerra et al. 1992, Salmerón et al. 2011). The most common characteristics of this syndrome are dry twisted leaves accompanied by a considerable shrinkage of the lamina and increased rolling-up of the recurved margins, reducing evaporation and heat-stress (Kürschner 2004).

The cluster analysis of the investigated flora has emphasized a degree of dissimilarity higher than

50%. One of the 2 main clusters (B) is represented by the flora of sites 5 and 8, the only ones characterized by gypsum-clayey soil; in these sites *Tortula revolvens* was not found. The other main cluster (A) groups the flora of the remaining sites, surveyed on marl-gypsum and gypsum outcrops in different microclimatic conditions. A lower dissimilarity is recognized between sites 9–10, with the exclusive occurrence of *Cheilothela chloropus* and *Ptychostomum donianum*, and 11–12, with the exclusive presence of *Bryum radiculosum* and *Microbryum starckeanum*.

Comparing the Sicilian bryophyte flora with that of other Countries, a considerable affinity with the flora of the gypsum outcrops of Valencia and Iberian Peninsula as a whole can be observed (Table 2, Table 4), though the Spanish ones host some endemics and show a more marked environmental xericity. The affinity is less marked with the flora of the Emilia Romagna gypsum outcrops, the last one characterized by a lower occurrence of *Pottiaceae* species and higher taxonomic diversity at level of species and family. Apart from the basiphytic character of the species (Aleffi et al. 2014), the flora of Emilia Romagna gypsum outcrops is more diversified; indeed, it is represented by xeric taxa characterizing the most arid and exposed sites, as well as mesophytic or even hygrophytic taxa colonizing moist and shady microhabitats (Aleffi et al. 2014) not present on Sicilian gypsum outcrops. A certain affinity can be noted with the Emilian gypsum flora of the xeric sites, such as Onferno and Vena del Gesso, where the climatic or microclimatic conditions are closer to a typically Mediterranean context (Aleffi et al. 2014).

Regarding the functional groups of gypsophily, the most numerous functional group is represented by the gypsovags (64.7%), as well as highlighted for higher plants on gypsum outcrops of Italy (Musarella et al. 2018). It is possible to consider only one strictly gypsophyte, *Tortula revolvens*, and a group of wide gypsophytes, as *Crossidium squamiferum*, *C. crassinervium* and *Aloina* spp. Previously, the gypsicolous character of *Tortula revolvens* was highlighted by Privitera (1989) for Sicily, Guerra et al. (1993) for Albacete and Aleffi et al. (2014) for Emilia Romagna; moreover, this species, reported for the gypsiferous soils of Valencia region, was considered probably as the most characteristic taxon of the gypsum substrates (Guerra et al. 1993, Puche & Gimeno 1995). This species, showing a typically circum-Mediterranean distribution area, is very rare in Italy (Aleffi 2008), as well as in Europe (Hodgetts 2015). In Italy it has only been reported for gypsum outcrops of the Northern Apennines (Aleffi et al. 2014) and southern Sicily (Privitera 1989), and compact clayey soil in Calabria Region (Privitera & Puglisi 1999).

However, the strictly gypsicolous character cannot be extended to other taxa and, therefore, it is not possible to recognize an exclusive bryophyte flora of the gypsum substrates. Floras with similar floristic composition were found on loamy-limestone, clayey marl, calcarenite substrates in dry areas of Sicily and southern Italy (Lo Giudice & Galesi 2001, Privitera & Puglisi 1999, Puglisi 2010). The strict similarity to the flora of basic substrates suggests that, according to Aleffi et al. (2014), the gypsum substrate is not the only factor selecting the flora which is rather the result of a series of environmental and microclimatic factors that coexist in a site interfering each other. This is what is shown by the study of Bogdanović et al. (2009) where the effects of gypsum in the growth in vitro culture were tested on two non-gypsophilous moss species (*Bryum argenteum*, and *Atrichum undulatum*). These species were able to survive in cultures with added gypsum in increasing concentrations, suggesting that the gypsum is not the only stressor which can select the bryophytes.

Overall, the bryophyte flora of Sicilian gypsum outcrops shows a high naturalistic value, due to the occurrence of species of national and international scientific importance, such as the aforementioned *Acaulon triquetrum*, *Aloina brevirostris*, *Crossidium crassinervium*, *Gyroweisia reflexa*, *Syntrichia handelii*, *Tortula brevissima*, *Tortula revolvens*, *Tortula solmsii*, *Petalophyllum ralfsii*, the last one included in the Annex II of the 92/43/ECC Habitat Directive. Particularly interesting are *Syntrichia handelii*, reported in Italy only for Sicily and *Aloina brevirostris* for Valle d'Aosta Region (Aleffi et al. 2008) and recently for Sicily (unpublished data); both species are rare also in the Mediterranean Countries where often are reported as single record (Ros et al. 2013). A so valuable flora deserves a particular attention from the conservation point of view.

The gypsum habitats of Sicily, as well as of the other Italian sites, are not recognized as Habitats of European Community interest, unlike the Spanish ones included in the priority Habitat *1520 Iberian gypsum steppes (Gypsophiletalia). This problem also has arisen for the gypsum habitats of other European territories, such as Cyprus where, however, a specific LIFE project (LIFE-RIZOELIA) has

recognized this habitat and undertaken conservation actions included also the moss species *Tortula revolvens*.

As already highlighted in Musarella et al. (2018) for vascular flora, the Italian gypsum habitats could be included in the Habitat 1520* extending its current definition in the Manual of Habitat interpretation, also with the addition of Italian gypsophytes including the moss *Tortula revolvens*.

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<i>Hypnum cupressiforme</i> Hedw. var. <i>cupressiforme</i>	. . + +	Ms ps 4 4 b	Accidental
<i>Microbryum davallianum</i> (Sm.) R.H. Zander	+ +	Ts a 3 7 a	Gypsovag
<i>Microbryum starkeanum</i> (Hedw.) R.H.Zander + +	Ts a 3 7 d	Gypsovag
<i>Orthotrichum anomalum</i> Hedw. + .	Cu c 2 8 l	Accidental
<i>Orthotrichum diaphanum</i> Hedw.	Cu c 3 7 g	Accidental
<i>Pseudocrossidium hornschuchianum</i> (Schultz) R.H.Zander	+ . + + . + . . + . +	Tf c 3 7 a,f	Gypsovag
<i>Pseudocrossidium revolutum</i> (Brid.) R.H.Zander	+ . + . . . + + + . .	Tf c 3 8 a,e,f,g	Gypsovag
<i>Ptychostomum capillare</i> (Hedw.) & N.Pedersen	. . + . . . + + + . .	Tf c 4 7 e,f	Gypsovag
<i>Ptychostomum donianum</i> (Grev.) & N.Pedersen + + . .	Tf c 4 6 f	Accidental
<i>Ptychostomum imbricatulum</i> Holyoak & N.Pedersen	. . + + + + + .	Tf c 4 6 b,f,g	Gypsovag
<i>Ptychostomum torquescens</i> (Bruch & Schimp.) Ros & Mazimpaka + + +	Tf l 3 7 g	Gypsovag
<i>Rhynchostegiella tenella</i> (Dicks.) +	Mr ps 4 8 g	Accidental
<i>Rhynchostegium megapolitanum</i> (Blandow ex F.Weber & D.Mohr) +	Mr p 4 7 e	Accidental
<i>Scleropodium touretii</i> (Brid.) L.F.Koch	. + + + . + .	Mr p 3 6 f,g	Accidental
<i>Scorpiurium circinatum</i> (Bruch) & Loeske	. . + . . . + . . . + .	Mr p 3 7 g	Gypsovag
<i>Syntrichia handelii</i> (Schiffn.) S.Agnew Vondr. + . .	Tf c 3 7 l	Gypsovag
<i>Syntrichia laevipila</i> Brid.	. . + +	Tf c 4 6 g	Accidental
<i>Syntrichia ruralis</i> (Hedw.) F.Weber & Mohr var. <i>ruralis</i> +	Tf c 3 7 e	Gypsovag
<i>Syntrichia virescens</i> (De Not.) Ochyra +	Tf c 4 6 g	Accidental
<i>Timmiella anomala</i> (Bruch & Schimp.) Limpr. +	Tf c 5 5 e	Gypsovag
<i>Timmiella barbulooides</i> (Brid.) Mönk. + +	Tp p 5 8 e,f	Gypsovag
<i>Tortella flavovirens</i> (Bruch) Broth.	+ . . + . . + + . + . . .	Tf c 5 7 f,g,h	Gypsovag
<i>Tortella inclinata</i> (R.Hedw.) Limpr. + . . .	Tuft c 3 9 f	Gypsovag
<i>Tortella inflexa</i> (Bruch) Broth.	. +	Tp c 5 9 g,h	Gypsovag
<i>Tortella squarrosa</i> (Brid.) Limpr. + + . . .	Tf pc 2 9 b,f,g	Gypsovag
<i>Tortula atrovirens</i> (Sm.) Lindb. +	Tf c 5 6 a	Gypsovag
<i>Tortula acaulon</i> (With.) R.H.Zander +	Ts a 4 7 a	Gypsovag
<i>Tortula pilifera</i> (Hedw.) R.H. Zander +	Ts a 4 7 a	Gypsovag
<i>Tortula brevissima</i> Schiffn.	+	Ts c 2 8 a	Gypsovag
<i>Tortula marginata</i> (Bruch & Schimp.) Spruce	+ + .	Tf c 4 8 f,g	Gypsovag
<i>Tortula muralis</i> Hedw.	. . + . . . + + . . . + +	Tf c 2 8 f,g	Gypsovag
<i>Tortula revolvens</i> (Schimp.) G.Roth	+ + . + . . + . + + + +	Tf c 1 5 a,f,g	Strictly
<i>Tortula solmsii</i> (Schimp.) Limpr.	. +	Tf c 5 6 f	Gypsovag
<i>Trichostomum brachydontium</i> Bruch	. + + + + . . . + + + + +	Tf l 5 7 b,e,f,g	Gypsovag
<i>Trichostomum crispulum</i> Bruch	+ + + + + +	Tf c 4 8 a,b,e,f,g	Gypsovag
<i>Weissia condensa</i> (Voit) Lindb. +	Tf c 2 9 a	Gypsovag
<i>Weissia controversa</i> Hedw. var. <i>controversa</i>	. . . + . + + . . . + +	Tf c 4 6 b,d,e,g,h	Gypsovag
LIVERWORTS			
<i>Cephaloziella baumgartneri</i> Schiffn.	+ . + + +	Ms c 5 9 b,g	Gypsovag
<i>Fossombronia angulosa</i> (Dicks.)	. . . +	Ms a 7 5 b,g	Accidental
<i>Fossombronia caespitiformis</i> (Raddi) Not. ex Rabenh.	. . + . + . + +	Sc a 6 5 a,e	Gypsovag
<i>Fossombronia caespitiformis</i> subsp. <i>multispira</i> (Schiffn.) J.R.Bray et Cargill + . . . +	Sc a 4 4 e	Gypsovag
<i>Fossombronia pusilla</i> (L.) Nees var. +	Sc a 5 4 e	Accidental
<i>Petalophyllum ralfsii</i> (Wilson) Nees et Gottsche	+ +	St s 6 8 b,c	Accidental
<i>Southbya nigrella</i> (De Not.) Henriq. + . . .	Ms s 6 8 c	Gypsovag
<i>Southbya tophacea</i> (Spruce) Spruce + +	Ms c 7 8 c,g	Gypsovag

Table 2. Number of bryophyte taxa, ratio liverworts/mosses (l/m), pleurocarpous/acrocarpous (p/a) and Pottiaceae/mosses (Pot/m) in the gypsum outcrops of Sicily, Emilia Romagna region, Valencia and Iberian Peninsula.

	Taxa number	l/m	p/a	Pot/m
Sicily	85	0.10	0.17	0.58
Valencia	66	0.05	0.09	0.68
Iberian Peninsula	107	0.09	0.06	0.70
Emilia Romagna region	137	0.20	0.46	0.34

Table 3. Incidence of the life forms and life strategies of the bryophytes in the gypsum outcrops of Sicily.

Life forms	turf	mat	tuft	solitary	weft	cushion
%	65.5	1.4	8.4	4.8	3.5	3.5
Life strategies	colonist	perennial	annual shuttle	long-lived shuttle	short-lived shuttle	fugitive
%	65.5	15.5	11.9	3.5	2.4	1.2

Table 4. Percentage of the moss families in the gypsum outcrops of Sicily, Emilia Romagna region, Valencia and Iberian Peninsula.

	Sicily	Emilia-Romagna	Iberian	Valencia
Pottiaceae	58.4	36.9	70.4	68.2
Brachytheciaceae	11.7	14.9	5.1	11.1
Bryaceae	9.1	7.9	8.2	7.9
Dicranaceae	3.9	0.9	1.0	1.6
Funariaceae	3.9	0.9	2.1	1.6
Ditrichaceae	2.6	1.8		
Fissidentaceae	2.6	6.2	2.1	1.6
Orthotrichaceae	2.6	0.9		
Encalyptaceae	1.3	2.7	1.0	
Grimmiaceae	1.3	0.9	7.1	4.8
Hypnaceae	1.3	2.7	1.0	1.6
Amblystegiaceae	1.3	4.5		
Ephemeraceae	–	–	1.0	1.6
Bartramiaceae	–	0.9	1.0	
Mniaceae	–	6.2		
Neckeraceae	–	2.7		
Hylocomiaceae	–	1.8		
Leskeaceae	–	1.8		
Anomodontaceae	–	0.9		
Polytrichaceae	–	0.9		
Rhabdoweisiaceae	–	0.9		
Pseudoleskeaceae	–	0.9		
Seligeriaceae	–	0.9		
Thuidiaceae	–	0.9		

Fig. 1. Location of the investigated sites.

Fig. 2. Dendrogram of similarity of the bryofloras analyzed. Each site is coded by the number reported in the text.